

offspring:parent regression was the least variable of the estimates among populations (indicated by the low CV). Among the characters, mesocotyl length estimates were least variable.

This means early generation selection for seedling emergence should be more effective using mesocotyl length. Early generation selection using coleoptile and seedling length can be done only in selected crosses. Otherwise, selection would be more effective in later generations, accompanied by progeny testing. ■

Narrow sense heritability (Hn) estimates for mesocotyl, coleoptile, and seedling length in rice, measured by variance partitioning (VPSP) and offspring:parent F₃:F₂ regression (regr) and correlation (corr).

Cross	Hn estimates											
	Mesocotyl				Coleoptile				Seedling			
	VPSP	Regr	Corr	Mean	VPSP	Regr	Corr	Mean	VPSP	Regr	Corr	Mean
ITA212/Nato	53.7	64.7	49.0	55.8	30.4	40.7	54.2	41.8	48.3	26.7	35.0	36.7
TN1/Nato	30.6	71.4	63.3	55.1	67.6	35.6	48.7	50.6	30.3	27.4	33.2	30.3
TN1/ITA323	61.8	71.4	84.1	72.4	61.6	37.8	46.1	48.5	50.3	33.2	20.0	34.5
IR64/ITA212	50.0	52.7	63.1	61.1	21.2	18.7	26.2	22.0	35.2	26.5	40.3	34.0
Mean	49.0	65.1	64.9	59.7	45.2	33.2	43.8	40.7	41.0	28.5	32.1	33.9
CV	26.9	13.5	22.3	11.9	50.5	29.8	27.9	38.1	23.9	11.2	26.9	26.3

Genetic and cytoplasmic sources of IR varieties 1967-84

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Genetic diversity of cytoplasm sources for released varieties is important because genetic uniformity could lead to devastating disease epidemics. We used a computer program written in PASCAL to examine the pedigrees of 27 *Oryza sativa* L. IR lines released 1967-84.

The pedigrees show that the 27 varieties can be traced back to 26 ances-

tors, of which 5 appear only once. Ten ancestors comprise 75% of the relative genetic contribution. Three dominate in mean relative genetic contribution: Dee-geo-woo-gen, 16%; Cina, 12.6%; and Latisail, 12.6%. Dee-geo-woo-gen appears in the pedigree of 26 of the 27 varieties; Cina and Latisail are in the pedigrees of all varieties. This makes the 27 varieties examined more or less related. More ancestors have been integrated into recent varieties.

Four cultivars were ultimate maternal ancestors, and thus contributed cytoplasm to all 27 varieties (see table). Cina contributed its cytoplasm to 22 of the 27 varieties, and is the most

Cytoplasm parents for 27 varieties released at IRRI.

Cytoplasm parent	IR lines				
Nam Sagui 19 Cina	IR52	IR54			
	IR5	IR28	IR38	IR50	
	IR8	IR29	IR40	IR56	
	IR20	IR30	IR42	IR58	
	IR22	IR32	IR45	IR60	
	IR24	IR34	IR46		
Marong-Paroc Arikarai	IR26	IR36	IR48		
	IR43	IR44			
	IR62				

important contributor of both nuclear and cytoplasmic genes to the IR varieties. ■

Effect of germinating condition and plant growth regulator on rate of twin seedlings from polyembryonic rice

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Polyembryonic rice—characterized by twin seedlings—is a good genetical tool for apomixis research. We studied four selected heritable polyembryonic rices.

Adventitious embryos had low frequencies (2.6-5.1%). The apparent primary mode of polyembryonic rice is twin seedlings, but there is an internal relationship between the rate of twin seedlings and the rate of adventitious embryos.

We experimented with the effect of germinating condition on twin seedling rate in Shuang 3 (indica), Shuang 13

Table 1. Rates of twin seedlings under different germinating conditions.

Variety	Rate (%) of twin seedlings							
	Germinated in distilled water (25°C)	Germinated in N6 (25°C) (with no pretreatment)	Germinated in N6 media (25 °C) with wet pretreatment ^a (5 h)					
			0°C	10°C	20°C	30°C	40°C	50°C
Shuang 3 (indica)	41.0	48.4	17.1	65.8	67.5	75.0	70.5	42.5
Shuang 13 (indica)	5.3	7.7	5.3	12.9	7.4	13.2	6.9	16.6
Lu 52 (japonica)	6.5	13.2	6.7	11.1	7.9	13.1	8.8	24.5
Alixisini (japonica)	2.0	3.1	0	1.9	3.9	1.9	1.6	4.4

^a There was no germination at 60°C.

(indica), Lu 52 (japonica), and Alixisini (japonica). Germinating seeds without hulls resulted in higher rates of twin seedlings than germinating seeds with hulls. The highest increase was 3.8%.

The rate of twin seedlings increased when the germination test was done in

N6 media. The twin seedling rate varied with pregermination treatment at different temperatures (Table 1). The optimum pretreatment temperature was 50°C for two japonicas and one indica and 30°C for the other indica. At optimum temperature, the rate of twin seedlings

Table 2. Effect of plant growth regulators (10 mg/liter) on germination of polyembryonic rice.^a

Treatment ^b	Shuang 13 (indica)				Shuang 3 (indica)				Lu 52 (japonica)			
	G(%)	R(%)	WS (mg)	WT(mg)	G(%)	R(%)	WS (mg)	WT(mg)	G(%)	R(%)	WS (mg)	WT(mg)
CK	98.1	6.3	44.75	39.62	94.8	29.4	28.60	27.82	72.2	5.6	50.21	52.00
IAA	98.7	9.5	47.73	44.67	94.1	31.2	30.42	28.81	85.3	6.0	50.33	54.09
KT	98.2	7.2	42.63	39.50	93.3	31.7	25.89	25.60	91.3	6.7	55.17	55.20
GA ₃	98.2	8.7	42.59	43.68	89.5	27.0	24.14	23.38	79.1	5.1	48.72	46.50
2,4-D	97.5	10.8	36.45	38.55	93.9	38.1	26.60	25.89	86.0	8.0	48.28	49.58
6-BAP	97.6	10.4	42.81	43.27	92.9	30.7	30.60	28.39	80.0	9.4	51.93	57.80

^aG =germination percentage, R = rate of twin seedlings, WS = weight of single seedling, WT = weight of twin seedlings, ^bCK = distilled H₂O instead of plant growth regulator.

increased rapidly. At low (0°C) and high (60°C) temperatures, the seeds did not germinate.

The effect of five plant growth regulators IAA, KT, GA₃, 2,4-D, and 6-BAP on rate of twin seedlings was studied with polyembryonic rices Shuang 3, Shuang 13, and Lu 52. At concentrations of

10 mg/liter, all growth regulators except GA, increased the production of twin seedlings. The twin seedling rate increased more with 2,4-D and 6-BAP (Table 2).

Seedling growth of indicas Shuang 3 and Shuang 13 was stimulated by IAA at 10 mg/liter; average weight of

seedlings also increased. KT at 10 mg/liter increased seedling weight of japonica

Lu 52. The optimum concentrations for increasing the rate of twin seedlings were 1 mg 2,4-D/liter and 10 mg 6-BAP/liter. ■

Inheritance of photoperiod-sensitive genic male-sterile gene in rice

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CIS28-10S is a new photoperiod-sensitive genic male-sterile indica rice. To find the number of the gene for its male sterility in CIS28-10S, I set up a field experiment Apr-Sep 1990 with eight F₂ hybrids and eight B₁F₁ backcross hybrids, with CIS28-10S as the female parent.

There were 50 single plants/cross in the F₁, 117-307 in the F₂, and 79-161 in the B₁F₁ backcross. CIS28-10S was regarded as the check. The proportion of male sterile and male fertile plants was calculated 25 Jul-30 Aug.

The F₂ hybrids separated at nearly 1:3 sterile:fertile plants (Table 1). Fertility separation in the B₁F₁ backcross hybrids also was obvious, at nearly 1:1 (Table 2).

The male sterility of CIS28-10S appears to be controlled by a single dominant gene. ■

Table 1. Fertility of lower generation hybrids, Xiangtan, China, 1990.

Cross	Grain fertility of F ₁ hybrids (%)	Separation of F ₂ hybrids		Sterile plants: fertile plants
		Sterile plants (no.)	Fertile plants (no.)	
CIS28-10S/02428	79.1	76	231	1.000:3.039
CIS28-10S/R5	85.7	29	88	1.000:3.034
CIS28-10S/PC312	81.1	61	185	1.000:3.033
CIS28-10S/Guizhouger	10.3	66	181	1.000:2.742
CIS28-10S/Suweon 290	7.5	59	180	1.000:3.051
CIS28-10S/Japanese glutinous rice	63.9	71	220	1.000:3.099
CIS28-10S/Zixie glutinous rice	80.7	63	179	1.000:2.841
CIS28-10S/Teqing	86.7	51	160	1.000:3.137

Table 2. Fertility of B₁F₁ hybrids, Xiangtan, China, 1990.

Cross	Separation of F ₂ hybrids		Sterile plants: fertile plants
	Sterile plants (no.)	Fertile plants (no.)	
CIS28-10S//CIS28-10S/02428	41	39	1.0000:0.9512
CIS28-10S//CIS28-10S/R5	53	55	1.0000:1.0377
CIS28-10S//CIS28-10S/PC312	64	61	1.0000:0.9531
CIS28-10S//CIS28-10S/Guizhouger	70	12	1.0000:1.0286
CIS28-10S//CIS28-10S/Suweon 290	80	81	1.0000:1.0125
CIS28-10S//CIS28-10S/Japanese glutinous rice	63	66	1.0000:1.0476
CIS28-10S//CIS28-10S/Zixie glutinous rice	39	40	1.0000:1.0256
CIS28-10S//CIS28-10S/Teqing	49	48	1.0000:0.9796

Space limitations prevent *IRRN* from publishing solely yield data and yield component data from routine germplasm screening trials. Publication is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., multiple or unique resistances and tolerances, broad adaptability), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.